

International Newsletter on Physics Education

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Table of Contents

[A Call For Changes in Undergraduate Physics Education](#)

[Book Review: Teaching Introductory Physics by Arnold B. Arons](#)

[Sample Problem](#)

[Finding the Speed of Light with Marshmallows - A Take Home Lab](#)

[Physics Education Conferences](#)

[Internet Sites](#)

[Teaching Undergrad Science Through Problem Solving](#)

[Papers in Physics Education Research: 1996](#)

[ICPE Members](#)

A Call For Changes in Undergraduate

Physics Education

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Approximately 280 physicists from 28 countries met during the International Conference on Undergraduate Physics Education (ICUPE) from 31 July to 3 August 1996 in College Park, Maryland. The conference was organized around three themes:

- The undergraduate physics major as a passport to the workplace;
- Physics in the service of science and engineering students;
- The preparation of school teachers.

Each of the three themes were considered in terms of three implicit questions:

- What are appropriate goals?
- What do the results of research contribute?
- How can technology help?

From the opening moments of the conference it was recognized that while the past 50 years represented a unique period in the history of physics, these years had left physicists unprepared for the realities of the present environment. Coming out of the past half century, physicists are looking at new social and political priorities throughout the world. The competition for budgetary resources is keen in every nation and, compared with the past five decades, support for physics research is harder to come by. If our professional perceptions and expectations are to have contemporary usefulness, they must be recalibrated. Fortunately, as it emerged from the conference, there is a basis for guiding the recalibration and the message from the conference, taken as a whole, was a clear call: get on with making the changes in the undergraduate physics program needed to match the new environment.

A LOOK AT THE PAST

The explicit goal of the undergraduate major curriculum in physics is to prepare students for graduate study in physics. More specifically, to prepare students to pursue the Ph.D. in physics. This goal determines what physicists teach (the courses required and their content) and how physicists teach (pedagogical methods employed to present the content). This goal needs close scrutiny and review by the physics faculties of universities.

We need to change how we conceptualize the undergraduate major and undergraduate physics education more generally. This need is underscored when one examines the choices made by baccalaureate physicists. While the numbers vary from nation to nation, it is generally true that only a small fraction of the students who take the calculus-level introductory physics course go on to major in physics and only a small fraction of the students who major in physics go on to earn a Ph.D. in physics. The numbers for the United States are instructive:

Fraction of students in the calculus-level introductory physics class that major in physics	1 of 33
Fraction of students who major in physics that go on to graduate school in physics and obtain a Ph.D.	1 of 7

The numbers above show that less than 1 out of 200 students taking the calculus-level introductory physics course in the United States goes on to complete a Ph.D. in physics.

If physics baccalaureates do not go to graduate school in physics, where do they go? Again, numbers from the United States provide one answer. Over the past 40 years, approximately 200,000 baccalaureates in physics have been granted by institutions in the United States. About 20% of these 200,000 baccalaureates use their physics major as the foundation for farther study in another field: they either go to graduate school (computer science and engineering are common) or to a professional school (medicine, law, and business are common). About 40% of graduates take their physics degree and enter the workplace. About 30% continue their physics education in graduate school and somewhat less than half of these earn the Ph.D. in physics. (The remaining 10% do a variety of things.)

Over 60% of those physics baccalaureates who begin their working careers upon graduation go into the industrial sector. Within industry, physics baccalaureates can be found in many settings. Their job titles typically do not identify them as physicists, but rather as engineers, computer specialists, etc. Other graduates from physics departments take government positions or enter the teaching profession.

Fully two-thirds of the students who complete an undergraduate degree in physics pursue careers other than physics. Only 1 out of 7 students goes on to earn a Ph.D. in physics. These numbers reflect the past and present in the United States.

There is remarkable similarity between the numbers above, based on U.S. data, and data collected in the United Kingdom. In a study of the careers pursued by physics majors graduating with the class of 1980, it was found that 34% of the 1980 baccalaureates continued their education while 66% entered the workplace. Approximately 75% of those "working" graduates began their careers in industry and, as is the case in the United States, they filled positions with titles other than physicist.

Yet, in spite of these numbers from both the U.S. and the U.K., the undergraduate physics major and, to a lesser extent, the introductory course in physics are designed and the courses are taught as though all students are going to earn a Ph.D. and become research physicists. To put it another way, the needs of the majority of students, those who enter the workplace with their physics baccalaureate, are not explicitly considered in either course or curricular design.

THE CALL FOR CHANGE

With the decline in the support for basic research, the health of physics departments may in the future depend more on the undergraduate program than has been the case in the past; thus, it behooves physics faculty to effectively serve the majority of students who pursue careers other than one in basic research. Physics faculty can take one step quite simply: begin to regard physics baccalaureates as fellow professionals. The baccalaureate in engineering, for example, is considered a terminal degree and those holding an engineering baccalaureate are regarded as professional engineers. Engineering baccalaureates belong to professional engineering societies and associations both as members as well as in leadership roles. The same can be and should be true in physics.

While curricular changes in the undergraduate major may be called for, care and caution are advised. The current physics major does hone skills that physics alumni cite as an asset. Perhaps foremost among these skills is problem solving ability. At the same time, physics alumni in the United States and European industries specifically identify communication and interpersonal skills as very important and the undergraduate physics major does little to develop and strengthen these important skills. The 1995 European study further showed that industrialists identify the following skills, among others, as essential for success: learning to learn, the ability to work in a group, decision-making ability, personal discipline (including learning to learn by oneself), a sense of gaining the competitive edge, and a sense of service to the community

Pedagogical Methods

There is little research to guide course content or curricular design. By contrast, there is an abundance of evidence that calls for changes in pedagogical methods. Each day of the three-day conference research results were described and in addition, there were sample classes that showcased teaching strategies that were in line with the latest research and which were shown to be effective.

Subject-Oriented Learning

- Know facts, laws, terms, definitions
- Understand phenomena, arguments, explanations
- Recognize relations, patterns, structures
- Judge hypotheses, arguments, statements

Method-Oriented Learning

- Look up references, take notes
- Organize and plan work
- Visualize tables, graphs
- Structure, order material

- Write reports and protocols

Social Communication Component

- Listen
 - Use arguments
 - Question
 - Discuss
 - Cooperate, integrate
 - Present
-

As pedagogical research has shown convincingly, the standard end-of-chapter problem as well as the typical exam problems do not provide an accurate indication of actual understanding. Sample classes demonstrated how different types of questions could be used to bring understanding to basic physical ideas. One type of such question is qualitative in nature and has been called a concept question. Some years ago, Ibrahim Abou Halloun and David Hestenes designed a test of mechanics understanding, called the Force Concept Inventory, consisting of qualitative questions. Some of the questions were simple; none of the questions are tricky. The test has been administered widely with similar results: physics students who are successful end-of-chapter problem solvers do not do well. This has led to the organization of classrooms where qualitative questions play an important role. Another type of question demonstrated during one of the ICUPE sample classes was the question which requires the student to make assumptions to arrive at an answer. Order-of-magnitude (or Fermi-type) questions are examples of such open-ended questions. In a similar vein, Victor Weisskopf's "Search for Simplicity" which appeared in the *American Journal of Physics* in 1985 was cited as a source for discussion questions.

Another pedagogical strategy which was demonstrated and discussed at the conference involved students working in teams. In such cooperative efforts, students discuss physical concepts together and, in the process, teach each other. Common to all these pedagogical strategies is their interactive nature.

Active Learning

One theme that appeared and reappeared throughout the conference was "active learning". Or, to put it another way, pedagogical methods are called for which actively involve every student in the learning process. It was generally accepted that the classroom lecture does not accomplish this objective. Various laboratory-based and computer-based models were demonstrated in which students were working together in very active learning modes.

The active teaching/learning mode was deemed important for all students: physics majors, engineering students, non-science students, and future teachers. For the latter, future teachers, the active teaching/learning mode was judged particularly important. There is widespread international agreement that children in the elementary school grades learn best by doing. If teachers are to employ active teaching/learning methods in their classrooms, they must have the experience of having been taught and having learned in the same mode. Physics faculty must be models for future teachers.

Understanding the Nature of Science

The active teaching concept took another form which was recognized by virtually all conferees as very important, perhaps even essential. All students, and especially future teachers, need to understand the nature of science. How is science actually done? The means to answer this question and to provide students with an understanding of the nature of science is to involve students in investigations on topics for which the outcomes are not known. Students need to conduct a real investigation; asking appropriate questions, making predictions, engaging in experimentation, collecting data, analyzing data, identifying outcomes, and communicating results to peers.

Use of Technology

Technology can be a vehicle for developing a variety of active teaching/learning methods. Interactive computer activities, for example, is one way to engage students and to bring them actively into the course content. In several countries - for example, Germany, England, the United States - a variety of electronic methods are used.

Course Content

An active teaching/learning style coupled with an independent investigation carries the obvious consequence: a leaner syllabus. The fact that physicists attempt too much in their courses, especially introductory-level courses, was widely recognized. In the United Kingdom, for example, there is the challenge to include at most two-thirds the content currently in the three-year honors physics degree program. In spite of an implied leaner syllabus, the support for an active teaching/learning methodology was prompted by research data that show enhancements, sometimes significant, in student understanding. These results were cited from studies for both small and relatively large class sizes. Thus, less may indeed be more.

SUMMARY

In the United States, the number of baccalaureates granted was at a 37-year low. Representatives from other countries, Germany for example, also cited dropping enrollments in physics. This decline coincides with a changing social environment within which physics must adapt. The dominant signal to emanate from ICUPE was that changes are required in undergraduate physics education. The realities of the past are likely to be enhanced in the near term; namely, the majority of physics majors will enter the job market with only their baccalaureate degree. Therefore, it behooves physicists to consider carefully the needs of contemporary employers and to prepare students to be marketable in the competitive employment arena.

A change in attitude about what a physicist is and what a physicist does is needed. In short, we need to professionalize the baccalaureate degree.

Finally, pedagogical changes are called for. Research into the learning process points toward an active teaching/learning environment as more effective. Such active methods will anticipate the work environment that most physics majors will enter upon graduation and they will also better prepare those students who plan a career in teaching. Technology can help, but no one suggested or implied that the changes called for will be easy to make or that they will be easy to implement. Technology does open the door for relatively international cooperation and learning from the experience of others. It was agreed that the consequences of "business as usual" could be dire for the health of physics departments on campuses around the world.

(To be published in the Proceedings of the International Conference on Undergraduate Physics Education. Used with permission.)

Book Review

Teaching Introductory Physics

by

Arnold B. Arons

(John Wiley and Sons, NY, 1997)

Edward F. Redish, University of Maryland, USA

One of the important tasks of a physics teacher is to help inspire a new crop of students to become physicists. In my personal trek towards becoming a professional physicist, I was lucky to have a young, inspiring high school teacher named Richard Powell. Later, I had the opportunity to work with and take courses with distinguished and well known physicists such as John Wheeler and Francis Low. My interactions with teachers provided formative highlights that helped both to develop my view of what physics is and the best ways to teach it. But today is not yesterday (it never is), and creating new physicists is turning into a much smaller (though still important) part of a physics instructor's responsibilities. Those of us in college and university physics departments need to significantly rethink our teaching as a result of the rapid expansion of the technological workplace and the growing need for workers and voters with a good understanding of science and technology. We must take on the responsibility of helping a large fraction of our students actually learn to use physics and understand physics in the highly restrictive context of their introductory physics course. For many of our students, that will be the only physics they ever choose to take. This makes our task much more difficult than when we could assume they would see the material again and again, and eventually understand physics when they came to teach it.

Fortunately, there are some tools that can provide valuable assistance. For decades, Arnold Arons has been helping physics teachers understand their students through insightful articles in journals such as *The American Journal of Physics*, *The Physics Teacher*, and *Daedalus*. With the publication of *Teaching Introductory Physics* by John Wiley and Sons, we have gained a tool for teachers of great and lasting value. The book consists of three parts. The first is a reprinting (with small corrections) of *A Guide to Introductory Physics Teaching*, Arons' 1990 volume that became an immediate classic. When it came out, I purchased a half a dozen copies and have been giving them to my Ph.D. students in physics education as an introduction to reflective teaching. It contains the distilled essence of 30 years of experience of a thoughtful and skilled teacher - one who listens carefully to his students and works to understand their difficulties. This part of the book is filled with surprising insights. (Try asking your introductory physics students whether an irregularly shaped object can have a well defined area. The results may surprise you.) It really becomes valuable when you realize that in rethinking your students' understanding of basic physics you are rethinking your own. The book contains many small subtle surprises and puzzles that delight, inform, and deepen one's understanding of introductory physics.

A useful aspect of this book for physics education researchers is that it includes many observations and comments that could be used as the start of a physics education research project. Observations such as Arons' are useful, but often benefit from more detailed

documentation. For example, when *A Guide to Introductory Physics Teaching* appeared, I read that "Students should be led to try the effects of magnets on their Scotch Tape® electroscopes and to ascertain that there is no interaction ... This paves the way for eliminating misconceptions such as repulsion between a north magnetic pole and a positive electric charge, and so on." I did not take much note of it. Later, I heard a report from the Physics Education Group at the University of Washington on a study of engineering students' responses to being taught about magnets.¹ They found that upon entry over 80% of their students confused electric charges and magnetic poles. After a traditional instruction, this number remained above 50%. I was both flabbergasted and distressed at hearing this. I have taught that subject off and on for over 25 years. Furthermore, I believed that I listen carefully to students and I am sensitive to the issue that students bring previous knowledge into their classroom. Yet I had never imagined such a confusion was common. Needless to say, I probed my class upon my return and found exactly the same results as the Washington group. Arons' book does contain many references to the research literature where some of his observations are documented, but the list is not intended to be complete.

An aspect of Arons' book that makes it both enlightening and enjoyable is his deep and abiding interest in the process of science - how it evolves as well as how students can begin to understand "how do we know ... why do we believe ... ?" He fills the book with philosophical and historical insights. The final chapters of part I on "Achieving Wider Scientific Literacy" and "Critical Thinking" are provocative and insightful. I consider them to be among the best essays ever written on the subjects.

The book's Part II has also been previously published as *Homework and Test Questions for Introductory Physics Teaching*. It presents more than 400 thought-provoking conceptually challenging problems in introductory physics. I have used them as starting points for building supplementary homework and exam problems for my classes since the book first appeared in 1994 and have been very pleased with the results. However, the casual user should note that the problems are sometimes worded in Arons' characteristic eloquent style. I find that for my classes I often have to rewrite them using simpler vocabulary and shorter sentences. Also, many students will not like them! These problems require that the student actually think about the physics. In my experience, many students would prefer to do an hour of mindless plug-and-chug to ten minutes of thinking. When used with care and persistence, these problems can be used as part of a consistent effort to introduce beginning students to the joy of figuring things out. The paperback version of Part II could be used as a supplement to a traditional textbook.

The third part of the book is the only part that is truly new. Part III is a 150-page monograph on teaching the subject of energy. It assumes that the reader has a well-developed understanding of the concepts of force and Newton's laws, and has mastered the basic elements of calculus. It is therefore more appropriately a guide for the teacher. (Even if you wanted your students to use it you would have trouble. Wiley has unfortunately made the decision not to publish this part separately, so it can only be purchased together with the teacher's guide in part I - not something a teacher could easily require students to purchase.) Arons carefully analyzes the concepts of energy and points out many subtleties with care and clarity. A number of activities are presented in a way that can conveniently be adapted to serve a lab or extended class discussions.

As is typical with Arons, however, much of the material in part III has "some assembly required". This is not an "off-the-shelf" cookbook of lessons. Just as he requires his students build the

concepts of physics for themselves, he implicitly expects his physics teachers to construct lessons and activities for their students for themselves, with helpful guidance from his materials. All in all, this volume is probably the best introduction to physics teaching available. I strongly recommend it to every teacher of introductory physics.

(Some sample problems from the book are on page 5. All

quotes used with permission.)

1 P. A. Krause, P. S. Shaffer, and L. C. McDermott, "Using research on student understanding to guide curriculum development: An example from electricity and magnetism", *AAPT Announcer* **25** (Dec., 1995) 77.

Sample Problems from Arnold Arons' Book *Homework and Test Questions for Introductory Physics Teaching*

Problem 3.40: Consider the situation illustrated here: the system accelerates when object B is released. The inertial effects of both the string and the pulley are negligible. The string is essentially unstretchable.

1. How does the acceleration of body A compare with that of body B? Are the accelerations equal or different? If different, which is larger? Explain your reasoning.
2. While the system is accelerating, how does the magnitude of the force exerted by the string on cart A compare with the weight of body B? Is the force exerted by the string on cart A smaller than the weight of body B? (An algebraic solution is not being called for; the reasoning should be performed quantitatively.) Explain your reasoning.
3. Suppose that m_B is increased while m_A remains unchanged. What will happen to the acceleration of the system? Will it increase, decrease, or remain unchanged? What will happen to the force the string exerts on body A? What will happen as m_B is increased further and m_A becomes very small relative to m_B ? Explain your reasoning.
4. Describe what will happen to the acceleration of the system and to the force the string exerts on m_A if the changes in part (c) are reversed and m_B becomes very small relative to m_A . Explain your reasoning.
5. Suppose carts A and B are connected by a rope with significant mass rather than by a massless string. Will the acceleration of the system be uniform or nonuniform? If nonuniform, will the acceleration increase or decrease after release of cart B? Explain your reasoning.
6. What difficulties would be introduced into the problem if the string or rope connecting the two bodies were stretchable rather than unstretchable?

Problem 9.9: Is it possible to connect two identical batteries to make two bulbs in series light just as brightly as one alone across one battery? If so, sketch and explain the circuit diagram. If not, explain your reasoning.

Problem 9.11: You have heard the term "short circuit" used in a variety of circumstances. Define this term *operationally*. (This means that you must describe actions and observations of results of these actions. Words or synonyms alone are not adequate.)

Finding the Speed of Light with

Marshmallows-A Take-Home Lab

Robert H. Stauffer, Jr., Cimarron-Memorial High School, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA

I have heard that at 16 years old, Albert Einstein constantly wondered what it would be like to ride on a beam of light. Students in physics always seem to be fascinated by the properties of light. However, speed-of-light demonstrations often require extensive preparation or expensive equipment. I have prepared a simple classroom demonstration that the students can also use as a take-home lab.

The activity requires a microwave oven, a microwave-safe casserole dish, a bag of marshmallows, and a ruler. (The oven must be of the type that has no mechanical motion-no turntable or rotating mirror. If there is a turn-table, remove it first.) First, open the marshmallows and place them in the casserole dish, completely covering it with a layer one marshmallow thick. Next, put the dish of marshmallows in the microwave and cook on low heat. Microwaves do not cook evenly and the marshmallows will begin to melt at the hottest spots in the microwave. (I learned this from our Food Science teacher Anita Cornwall.) Heat the marshmallows until they begin to melt in four or five different spots. Remove the dish from the microwave and observe the melted spots. Take the ruler and measure the distance between the melted spots. You will find that one distance repeats over and over. This distance will correspond to half the wavelength of the microwave, about 6 cm. Now turn the oven around and look for a small sign that gives you the frequency of the microwave. Most commercial microwaves operate at 2450 MHz.

All you do now is multiply the frequency by the wavelength. The product is the speed of light.

Example:

$$\text{Velocity} = \text{Frequency} \times \text{Wavelength}$$

$$\text{Velocity} = 2450 \text{ MHz} \times 0.122 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Velocity} = 2.99 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}$$

This works in my physics class, often with less than 5% error. Then the students can eat the marshmallows.

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Physics Education Conferences

IUPAP Sponsored:

VI Inter-American Conference on Physics Education

30 June - 3 July 1997

Cordoba, Argentina

- New technologies in the classroom
- Updating the physics curriculum at all levels
- Physics education's role in teacher preparation
- History & epistemology of physics education

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smf1.fciencias.unam.mx/boletin/Jul-96/varia/argen.html

Creativity in Physics Education

18 - 24 August 1997

Sopron, Hungary

- New Approaches in physics teaching
- Cultures of international science teaching
- Computer and multimedia in physics
- New technology and equipment in experiments
- Workshops on creative computer programming, experiments, & problem solving

Registration fee: US\$250.

Contact:

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Other Conferences of Interest:

First European Conference on Physics Teaching in Engineering

4- 6 June 1997

Copenhagen, Denmark

- What engineers & industry need from physics
- Teaching strategies
- Small/large groups
- Inclusion of modern physics
- Development of learning skills on physics
- Computer-aided teaching

Registration fee: 800DKR

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Erik Oehlenschlaeger, PTEE 1997

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<http://www.ptee97.cph.ih.dk>

Justification & Enrollment Problems in Education Involving Mathematics or Physics

22-26 August 1997

- The nature & causes of the enrollment problem
- The nature & causes of the justification problem
- Do mathematics & physics have special properties or roles in relation to enrollment and justification problems?

Registration fee: 1500 DKR

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<http://mmf.ruc.dk/conf/1an.htm>

First Conference of the European Science Education Research Association (ESERA)

2-6 September 1997

Rome, Italy

- Teacher education
- Experimental activities in science education
- The popularization of science
- Educational methodology
- Teaching/learning processes in science education

Registration fee: US\$150 for ESERA members

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Project Organization as Form of Study at Universities

14-22 September 1997

The conference will study student project work, concentrating on interdisciplinarity, project organization, & influence on the student. Projects will be looked at from the perspectives of the teacher, the student, epistemology, etc.

Registration fee: 2200DKR, 1000DKR for students

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<http://www.ruc.dk/eng/aktuelt/jubikonf.html>

Internet Sites

Compiled by Dan Campbell, Associate Editor

Indexes

Museums

www.icom.org/vlmp

Index of every museum in the world that has a web page. Organized by country. All kinds of museums including art, science, cultural, zoos, etc.

Astromonical WWW Resources

venus.ast.univie.ac.at/Links/net-www.html

Comprehensive list of every astronomy resource that has a web page. Includes observatories, societies, university departments, astronomers' personal pages, etc.

The Nobel Prize Internet Archive

nobelprizes.com

Includes a short biography of every Nobel Prize winner in each category along with a description of what they did to win their prize. Each person's page also has links to other pages dedicated to that person. Includes pages, links, and commentary for the Ig Nobel prizes too.

Physics Lover's paradise

138.37.6.1/~zgap4027/physics.html

Big index of web sites devoted to famous physicists, institutions, astronomy, nuclear, particle, & theoretical physics.

Also links to various physics periodicals and places from which to start a search for information. Overall, a very informative page.

Science in the Classroom

Project Physics

www.amersol.edu.pe/~kacres/project

Great locally-produced site with several projects emphasizing creativity and scientific principles that students can work on as a team.

Illusionworks

www.illusionworks.com

Commercial site that advertises itself as having the largest collection of illusions anywhere. Great source of puzzles, science projects, and of course illusions. With index to other illusion and

puzzle sites and a bibliography.

University of Queensland Department of Physics

www.physics.uq.oz.au:8001/

See especially pages for the PH128 HyperTextbook (an on-line text), the Physics Museum (pictures and description of old experimental equipment), and the Physics in Action program (with a physics puzzle to solve).

C-ship: Relativistic Ray Traced Images

www.fourmilab.ch/cship/cship.html

C-ship helps the user understand Einstein's theory of Special Relativity through computer-synthesized images. Images show what observers on the ship see as it approaches light speed. Demonstrates Lorentz shift, dialation of time, aberration of light, Doppler shift, etc.

Virtual Laboratory

<http://jersey.uoregon.edu/vlab/>

Series of experiments using Java Applets for students in mechanics, thermodynamics, astrophysics, and electricity.

Lecture Demonstration Sites

Here is a list of university physics departments with good lecture demonstration catalogs. This list is by no means all-inclusive or even necessarily the best, just some good ones I have noticed.

University of Maryland

www.physics.umd.edu/deptinfo/facilities/lecdem/

University of Oregon

guernsey.uoregon.edu/~phdemo/dem.html

University of Glasgow

www.physics.gla.ac.uk/~kskeldon/PubSci/exhibits/

Virginia Tech

www.phys.vt.edu/teaching/demos.html

North Carolina State University

www2.ncsu.edu/ncsu/pams/physics/Edu_Resources/demoroom/demoroom.html

Case Western Reserve University

www.cwru.edu/CWRU/Dept/Artsci/phys/courses/demos/front.htm

California Polytechnical University, Pomona

www.intranet.csupomona.edu/~physics/demos.html

University of Melbourne

www.ph.unimelb.edu.au/lecdem/nick1.htm

Society for Amateure Science

www.eskimo.com/~billb/scied.html

This fascinating site could also be in the Science in the Classroom category as it is filled with interesting projects as well as demonstrations. Make your own clouds, electrostatic motor, holograms, and other fun science projects at very low cost. Site also contains some dangerous experiments that generate hot plasma and large charges of electricity.

And Finally**Physics Humor**

www.cyberspc.mb.ca/~dcc/phys/humor.html

Large index of physics and other academic humor sites.

Teaching Undergraduate Science Through Problem Solving

Elizabeth Deane, University of Western Sydney, Nepean, Australia

The real world of the practicing scientist is a world of problem solving. Choosing an effective and efficient experimental pathway to solve such problems is also, in itself, a problem-solving exercise. Which protocol of an array of possible protocols will best meet your needs? How much will it cost? How long will it take? How feasible is it in your laboratory and, most importantly, will it give you a solution? A whole series of questions need to be answered before the wise scientist proceeds. In this real world of science, the practitioner uses a range of approaches: peer discussion, reading the research literature and technical material, and trial & error to name but a few.

How then do we prepare our undergraduates for this real world of practice? The majority of undergraduate science courses in Australia, particularly in the earlier years of the program, are taught through a didactic approach with lectures, tutorials, and structured laboratory "experiences". Even in the latter years of the course, the laboratory experience is still fairly structured, presumably with a view to not only provide students with a set of marketable competencies, but also to provide them with what academics perceive to be skills appropriate to the discipline. To complicate matters, the knowledge base, and indeed the technical competency, of science is continuously expanding, making the task of designing science, and in particular, laboratory programs even more difficult.

In our science courses we strive to develop strategies which provide students with the wherewithal to meet the needs their future workplace. We try to ensure that students acquire not only a sound knowledge base, but a set of valuable laboratory competencies. Nevertheless, we need to achieve more; we need to instill in these students the capacity to extend beyond what we have been able to offer in their course work, to develop the skills of lifelong learners.

In the B.Sc. (Biological Sciences) offered by the University of Western Sydney, Nepean campus, we have had the opportunity to develop a degree course with these ideas in mind. The course itself only commenced in 1992 with 40 students. This small number made it feasible to try different approaches to enhance student learning. One such approach has been the development of a third year subject in Immunology in which the laboratory activities are completely directed at investigating a real-world problem and the content areas are derived from current research literature.

The structure of the subject aims to develop a learning environment which is student-focused, not teacher-focused and has three components:

1. Review of research literature,
2. Presentations by researchers in the field,
3. Problem-solving approach to developing laboratory competencies

In component 1, students working in pairs are required to access a research paper in three major designated areas of immunology. They then analyze the conceptual framework and rationale of the paper, critically evaluate the methodology, and examine the results. Each pair is required to present a 5 to 10 minute oral critique of each paper to the class; and all students are required to

write a review of all three major areas of the course, incorporating information from papers presented in class.

Component 2 of this subject consists of guest lectures presented by researchers in immunology, the intent of this component being to bring together the student reading and analysis of research literature and their own experience in developing experimental protocols.

Component 3 is concerned with developing in students an appreciation of their laboratory activities through a problem-solving approach. Students are provided with a set of problems which are either concerned with immunological function or require an understanding of the use of immunological methods. Again, students work in pairs, investigate possible experimental solutions, discuss it with their lecturer and each other, and finally set up and undertake their experiments, from go to whoa, including ordering and preparing all their own materials and cleaning up!

Early on it becomes clear that students needed a resource base which would focus their thinking and provide them with guidelines as to the appropriate use and value of specific experimental techniques. While students undertaking the program had already been exposed to a range of laboratory experiences, it was apparent that they needed some direction in how these experiences/techniques could be applied in different situations. As a consequence, as well as developing a series of problems, support material was developed using a worldwide web browser. This support base consists of theoretical material related to immunological structure, function, and dysfunction; practical exercises with pictorial outcomes relating to the exploration of this theoretical base and a series of references to each topic area.

The use of the web browser permits access from the document being looked at to the wider information network of the web. This aspect of the material ensures that the database maintains its currency and with continued updating of the text, continues to be a useful, relevant source.

In total, this approach is designed to develop student skills in:

- Problem conceptualization and evaluation.
- Accessing research literature.
- Evaluation of different laboratory methodology.
- Peer discussions
- Design, implementation, and evaluation of laboratory outcomes.

This subject has now run for three years, each year and each group of students has been different. The problems have evolved and the web-based support material is still growing as more material and results are added. The delivery of this subject is an intensely personal experience; I have benefited as an academic as this approach maintains my currency in the research area. However, I am no longer totally in control of the subject; it is driven by the student needs and ideas and, just in case you think this approach can't be used by others, in 1996, as I was on study leave, the subject was directed by an immunology researcher who was external to the institution. Her enthusiasm and satisfaction matched mine.

(This article originally appeared in Uniserve Science News, Nov 96. Used with permission.)

Papers in Physics Education Research: 1996

This list includes papers published in a variety of journals that may be of interest to researchers in physics education and to physics teachers interested in making their classrooms more effective. Papers have been selected that focus on high school or college level physics teaching, though we may occasionally include papers described work with younger students if they seem relevant.

The American Journal of Physics, Vol. 64

- R. Di Stefano, "The IUPP evaluation: What we were trying to learn and how we were trying to learn it", No. 1, January 1996, pp. 49-57.
- R. Di Stefano, "Preliminary IUPP results: Student reactions to in-class demonstrations and to the presentation of coherent themes", No. 1, January 1996, pp. 58-68.
- Diane J. Grayson and Lillian C. McDermott, "Use of the computer for research on student thinking in physics", No. 5, May 1996, pp. 557-565.
- Robert J. Beichner, "The impact of video motion analysis on kinematics graph interpretation skills", No. 10, October 1996, pp. 1272-1277.
- David Hammer, "More than misconceptions: Multiple perspectives on student knowledge and reasoning and an

appropriate role for education research", No. 10, October 1996, pp. 1316-1325.

- Richard N. Steinberg, Graham E. Oberem, and Lillian C. McDermott, "Development of a computer-based tutorial on the photoelectric effect", No. 11, November 1996, pp. 1370-1379.
- William J. Leonard, Robert J. Dufresne, and Jose P. Mestre, "Using qualitative problem-solving strategies to highlight the role of conceptual knowledge in solving problems", No. 12, December 1996, pp. 1495-1503.

International Journal of Science Education, Vol. 18

- Ted Graham and John Berry, "A hierarchical model of the development of student understanding of momentum", No. 1, January-February 1996, pp. 75-90.
- Josh Gutwill, John Frederiksen, and Michael Ranney, "Seeking the causal connection in electricity: shifting among mechanistic perspectives", No. 2, March 1996, pp. 43-162.
- Susan M. Stocklmayer and David F. Treagust, "Images of electricity: how do novices and experts model electric current?", No. 2, March 1996, pp. 163-178.
- Abdelmajid Benseghir and Jean-Louis Closset, "The electrostatics-electrokinetics transition: historical and educational difficulties", No. 2, March 1996, pp. 179-191.
- Abdeljalil Metioui, Claude Brassard, Jude Levasseur, and Michel Lavoie, "The persistence of students' unfounded beliefs about electrical circuits: the case of Ohm's law", No. 2, March 1996, pp. 193-212.
- David F. Treagust, Allan G. Harrison, and Grady J. Venville, "Using an analogical teaching approach to engender conceptual change", No. 2, March 1996, pp. 213-229.
- Keith S. Taber and Mike Watts, "The secret life of the chemical bond: students' anthropomorphic and animistic references to bonding", No. 5, July-August 1996, pp. 557-568.

- Jayashree Ramadas, Shrish Barve, and Arvind Kumar, "Alternative conceptions in Galilean relativity: inertial and non-inertial observers", No. 5, July-August 1996, pp. 615-629.
- Ruth Stavy and Dina Tirosh, "Intuitive rules in science and mathematics: the case of 'more of A -- more of B' ", No. 6, September 1996, pp. 653-667.
- Dina Tirosh and Ruth Stavy, "Intuitive rules in science and mathematics: the case of 'Everything can be divided by two' ", No. 6, September 1996, pp. 669-683.
- T.P. Olsen, P.W. Hewson, and L. Lyons, "Preordained physics and student autonomy: The nature of laboratory tasks in physics classrooms", No. 7, October-November 1996, pp. 775-90.
- Igal Galili, "Students' conceptual change in geometrical optics", No. 7, October-November 1996, pp. 847-868.
- Mike Watts and Keith S. Taber, "An explanatory gestalt of essence: students' conceptions of the 'natural' in physical phenomena", No. 8, December 1996, pp. 939-954.

Journal of the Learning Sciences, Vol. 5

- David Hammer, "Misconceptions or p-prims: How may alternative perspectives of cognitive structure influence instructional perceptions and intentions?", No. 2, pp. 97-127.

Journal of Research on Computing in Ed., Vol. 28

- Herman Weller, "Assessing the impact of computer-based learning in science," Summer, 1996, pp. 461-485.
- David Ayersman, "Reviewing the hypermedia-based learning research," Summer, 1996, pp. 500-525.

Journal of Research in Science Teaching, Vol. 33

- Maher Z. Hashweh, "Science teachers' epistemological beliefs in teaching", No. 1, January 1996, pp. 47-63.
- C. W. J. M. Klaassen and P. L. Lijnse, "Interpreting students' and teachers' discourse in science classes: an underestimated problem?", No. 2, February 1996, pp. 115-134.
- Wolff-Michael Roth and Kenneth Tobin, "Staging Aristotle and natural observation against Galileo and (stacked) scientific experiment or physics lectures as rhetorical events", No. 2, February 1996, pp. 135-157.
- Stanley J. Sobolewski and Rodney L. Doran, "Replication of a path analysis model of secondary physics enrollments: 20 years later", No. 5, May 1996, pp. 501-512.
- Allan Feldman, "Enhancing the practice of physics teachers: mechanisms for the generation and sharing of knowledge and understanding in collaborative action research", No. 5, May 1996, pp. 513-540.
- Wobbe de Vos and Adri H. Verdonk, "The particulate nature of matter in science education and in science", No. 6, June 1996, pp. 657-664.
- Paul J. Germann and Roberta J. Aram, "Student performances on the science processes of recording data, analyzing data, drawing conclusions, and providing evidence", No. 7, September 1996, 773-798.
- Wolff-Michael Roth, Corolyn Woszcynsa, and Gillian Smith, "Affordances and constraints of computers in science education", No. 9, November 1996, pp. 995-1017.
- Evinella Alexopoulou and Rosalind Driver, "Small-group discussion in physics: Peer interaction modes in pairs and fours", No. 10, December 1996, pp. 1099-1114.

- Robert E. Bleicher, "High school students learning science in university research laboratories", No. 10, December 1996, pp. 1115-1133.

Journal of Science Education and Technology, Vol. 5

- Eileen Lob Lewis, "Conceptual change among middle school students studying elementary thermodynamics", No. 1, March 1996, pp. 3-31.
- J. A. Cilliers, P. Kruger, I. Basson, and P. A. Kirschner, "Psychometric testing as a predictor of student performance in first year physics practicals", No. 1, March 1996, pp. 47-57.
- Bat-Sheva Eylon, Miky Ronen, and Uri Ganiel, "Computer simulations as tools for teaching and learning: using a simulation environment in optics", No. 2, June 1996, pp. 93-110.
- Wolff-Michael Roth, "The co-evolution of situated language and physics knowing", No. 3, September 1996, pp. 171-191.

Physics Education, Vol. 31

- Robin Millar and Jarnail Singh Gill, "School students' understanding of processes involving radioactive substances and ionizing radiation", No. 1, January 1996, pp. 27-33.
- Michael Prosser, Paul Walker, and Rosemary Millar, "Differences in students' perceptions of learning physics", No. 1, January 1996, pp. 43-48.
- Ricardo Trumper, "A cross-college age study about physics students' conceptions of force in pre-service training for high school teachers", No. 4, July 1996, pp. 227-236.
- Peter Adamczyk and Mike Willson, "Using concept maps with trainee physics teachers", No. 6, November 1996, pp. 374-381.

The Physics Teacher, Vol. 34

Cedric J. Linder and Greg Hillhouse, "Teaching by conceptual exploration", September 1996, pp. 332-338.

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